

SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE TRANSLATION OF NEOLOGISMS

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Abstract: From the analysis of the definitions of the concept of “neologism” by various researchers, two points of view become obvious, consisting in the fact that the term “neologism” is applied as to neoplasms, that is, to newly created on the material of the language, in full accordance with the word-formation models existing in the language, words or phrases denoting a new, previously unknown, non-existent concept, subject, branch of science, occupation, profession, etc., for example, reactor – nuclear reactor, biocide – biological warfare, etc., and actually neologisms, that is, newly created synonyms for a word already available in the language to denote a known concept, which, however, convey connotative shades, i.e. the accompanying semantic and stylistic shades of the word, which are superimposed on its main meaning, as well as to words in a new meaning, for example, the word boffin (a scientist engaged in secret work, most often for military purposes) is a close synonym of the word scientist, but has a different semantic connotation.

Key words: abbreviation, classification of transformations, semantic peculiarities, translation techniques, classifications of translation transformations.

Introduction

In the sphere of everyday life, a popular expression to characterize a modern person is, for example, the expression stress puppy (“child of stress”) – a person accustomed to living a stormy, energetic life.

The growth of divorces brings with it such neologisms as tug-of-love (tug-of-war) – “the child of divorced parents”; new feminism – “the concept of new family

values”. At the same time, there are problems in raising children in wealthy families, which brings the appearance of such neologisms: bratlash by backlash against parents raising obnoxious offspring; they do so by living relatively frugally, making children their own allowances and letting them spend only what they’ve earned”, financial parenting “financial services and education offered to the children of wealthy parents”.

In the fields of fine art, theatrical life, cinema and television, we also find quite a lot of innovations: kinetic art “art that uses moving things”, revivalism “a school of modern painting that returns to the old forms and techniques of fine art”; son et lumiere “theater using sound and light effects”; kidvid “TV shows for children”; video-camera “video camera”; inflight movies “movies that are shown during a flight on board an airplane” and other neologisms.

Many interesting neologisms can also be found in such spheres of human activity as education, the professional sphere, economics, feminist movements, paranormal research, and the like. So, for example, a new semantic group are neologisms associated with permissible visits to Earth by aliens from outer space, for example: UFO (Unidentified Flying Object) – UFO (unidentified flying object) and the formation of this English abbreviation type ufology – ufology; extra-terrestrials – aliens; saucer feet – prints left by flying saucer, etc. Especially a large number of new lexical units appeared in connection with the development of computer technology. For example: personal computer (PC) – personal computer; multi-user – a computer for several people; neurocomputer – an electronic analogue of the human brain; hardware – computer parts; software – computer program; megabyte of computer memory – megabyte (name of a special unit) of computer memory; doxware – computer program created to destroy computer programs; to trouble-shoot – destroy part of the data in computer memory, etc.

Of course, a large number of neologisms arise in connection with the social changes that are taking place in English-speaking countries. One of the most

common common phenomena, especially characteristic of the UK, is the so-called feminist movement, that is, the movement of women for equality in rights with men. Thanks to this movement, many new lexical units have emerged, for example: the Lib Movement is a feminist movement; libber libbie is a participant or supporter of the feminist movement, etc.

The names with the second component -man, for example, have also changed: instead of cameraman, camera operator is more often used, instead of fireman – firefighter, instead of policeman – police-officer, instead of chairman – chairman, instead of Congressman – Congressperson (although many words with the second component -person instead of -man are often used with a touch of humor and irony), even in the church mankind is replaced by people. At the same time, the names of women's professions are replaced with neutral in form, for example, instead of stewardess, flight attendant is used, or if men are employed in these professions, they receive a male “marker”, for example: male nurse, male secretary, male exotic dancer, etc.

There is also some heterogeneity in the composition of these lexical innovations due to the reasons for their appearance, their stability in the language, and the frequency of use. And in their further fate, when some of them are firmly embedded in the language, while others are less stable and may go out of use after a relatively short period of time.

The problem of translation transformations is one of the most urgent in modern translation studies. In order to correctly reproduce the content of a foreign text, translators’ resort to various transformations that completely or partially change the structure of the original sentences. Translation performs an extremely important social function. In the process of translation, it often turns out to be impossible to use the meanings of words and phrases that are offered in the dictionary, there is often a need to deviate from system equivalents, that is, there is a need for translation transformations.

Discussion

Recent studies show that to date there is no single system of classification of transformations, moreover, there are different opinions about which translation techniques relate to transformations. Translation is a comparison of two language systems at all levels. The linguistic level of translation is the lowest in the hierarchy of translation tasks, but it is extremely necessary for the full transmission of the content of the original text. It is clear that the translator will need to convey not only the sum of meanings encoded in sentences, but also information related to the culture, traditions, tastes of the nation, which requires going beyond a purely linguistic language system (the highest level of translation) and is called extralinguistic information or background knowledge. But, as V.S. Vinogradov notes, translation begins from a purely linguistic level [1, p. 18].

In the process of translation, it often turns out to be impossible to use a literal vocabulary, and the translator resorts to the transformation of the internal form of a word or phrase or its complete replacement, that is, to a translation transformation.

According to the definition given in the linguistic encyclopedia by A.A. Selivanova, transformation is the basis of most translation techniques, which consists in changing the formal (lexical or grammatical transformations) or semantic (semantic transformations) components of the source text while preserving the information intended for transmission [2, p. 536]. In general, this term is used in many branches of linguistics and has many different definitions. To define the term "translation transformation", it is necessary first to understand the meaning embedded in it. Various scientists (L.S. Barkhudarov, A.D. Schweitzer, J.Y. Retsker, V.N. Komissarov, L.K. Latyshev, etc.) in different ways interpret this concept. For example, according to J.J. Retsker, transformations are logical thinking techniques that help to reveal the meaning of a foreign word in the context and find an analogue to it that does not coincide with the dictionary [3, p. 38]. In general, translation transformations can be considered interlanguage transformations, the restructuring of the source text or the replacement of its elements to achieve

translation adequacy and equivalence. The main characteristic features of translation transformations are the interlanguage character and purposefulness to achieve the adequacy of translation.

Today there are many classifications of translation transformations proposed by various authors. For example, L.K. Latyshev [4, p. 78] classifies translation transformations by the nature of deviation from interlanguage correspondences, and divides them into:

- 1) morphological – replacement of one categorical form by other or several;
- 2) syntactic – changing the syntactic function of words and phrases;
- 3) stylistic – changing the stylistic coloring of a text segment;
- 4) semantic – changing not only the form of expression of the content, but also the content itself, with which the situation is described;
- 5) mixed – lexico-semantic and syntactically-morphological.

Ya.Y. Retsker, in turn, distinguishes only two types of transformation: grammatical, which include substitutions of parts of speech or sentence members, and lexical, including concretization, generalization, differentiation of meanings, compensation of losses, arise in the process of translation [5, с. 87].

THE LIST OF THE USED LITERATURE

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